

Studies on the Decomposition Products of Ethereal Blue Perchromate by Ion-exchange Resins. Water-decomposition Product

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Barreswil¹ during the preparation of blue peroxychromic acid observed that the so-called blue peroxychromic acid on decomposition yielded chromic acid. Moissan² in isolating this blue acid from ethereal layer observed this so-called acid to become an oily liquid on concentration and decompose at a particular concentration. Rai and Prakash³ have shown that this blue compound on decomposition provides chromium dichromate, $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7)_3$.

An attempt has been made to ascertain the constitution of the water-decomposition product of the ethereal blue acid with the help of ion-exchange resins.

The blue perchromate was prepared by mixing ice-cold solutions of 5% $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ (50 ml), 2*N*- H_2SO_4 , and 20 vol. H_2O_2 (20 ml). It was extracted with ether, washed with ice-cold water, and decomposed in distilled water.

Procedure.—Several columns (6/75mm) of different cation and anion exchangers were prepared, washed, and the ions were separated from the solution of the water-decomposition product. Presence of Cr(III) and Cr(VI) was detected in the cationic and anionic portions of the above solution and these were eluted^{4,5} with 1:4 H_2SO_4 and a mixture of NaOH and NaCl and then estimated quantitatively by titrating against a standard thiosulphate solution. Results obtained are reported in Table I.

TABLE I

Volume of the water-decomposition product exchanged each time = 5ml. Thiosulphate soln. = *N*/97.58. Drop rate = 28-30 min. Column = 6/75 mm.

Resin.	Vol. of $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ soln. used in titrating					**Ratios.				
	*Exchanged & unoxidised.	*Unexchanged unoxidised.	Effluent.		Eluate oxidised.	b/a	a/e	b/c or d/e		c/d or e/e
	(a)	(b)	(c)	(d)	(e)					
Dowex 50(H)	6.50 ml	8.80 ml	6.45 ml	6.50 ml	2.10 ml	1.35	3.09	1.02		3.07
	6.50	8.80	6.50	6.50	2.10	1.35	3.09	1.02		3.09
	6.50	8.80	6.40	6.45	2.15	1.35	3.02	1.02		3.00
	6.50	8.80	6.45	6.50	2.10	1.35	3.09	1.02		3.07
Amberlite IR 120 (H)	6.30	8.70	6.30	6.30	2.00	1.38	3.15	1.04		3.15
	6.30	8.70	6.25	6.30	2.10	1.38	3.00	1.04		3.00
	6.30	8.70	6.30	6.30	2.00	1.38	3.15	1.04		3.15
Amberlite IRC 50(H)	6.90	9.10	6.80	6.80	2.30	1.32	3.00	1.00		2.95
	6.90	9.10	6.85	6.80	2.30	1.32	3.00	1.00		2.97
	6.90	9.10	6.80	6.80	2.35	1.32	2.93	1.00		5.95

**Ratios a/c and a/d in all cases = 1.

1. *Compt. rend.* 1848, 16, 1085.

2. *Ibid.*, 1883, 97, 96.

3. *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1954, 94, 275.

4. Samuelson, "Ion-Exchangers in Analytical Chemistry".

5. Gustavson, *J. Amer. Leather Chem. Assoc.*, 1950, 62, 164.

* In 5 ml of water-decomposition product.

TABLE II

Conditions same as in Table I.

Resin.	Vol. of $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ used in titrating				$\frac{b}{a}$	Ratios			
	*Unexchanged & unoxidised.	*Unexchanged & oxidised.	Eluate oxidised, or unoxidised.	Effluent oxidised.		$\frac{c}{a}$	$\frac{b}{c} \frac{c}{d}$	or $\frac{a}{d}$	$\frac{b}{c+d}$
	(a)	(b)	(c)	(d)	(e)	(f)	(g)	(h)	(i)
Amberlite	6.90 ml	9.10 ml	6.95 ml	2.25	1.30	1.00	1.32	3.00	1.00
IR 400 (Cl)	6.90	9.10	6.85	2.20	1.32	1.00	1.32	3.00	1.00
	6.90	9.10	6.90	2.30	1.32	1.00	1.32	3.00	1.00

* In 5 ml of water-decomposition product.

As evident from the tables, the amounts of Cr(III) and Cr(VI) are present in the cationic and anionic portions of the water-decomposition product solution in the ratio of 1:3. Hence, the formula of the compound is suggested as $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7)_3$.

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